

Original Research

Art as a Tool for Emotional Self-Regulation and Social Change in Family Support During Crisis Contexts

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Abstract: This research aims to answer the following question: Can artistic practices be an ideal tool for social work with families in traumatic situations? To this end, after conducting a keyword search, the results of artist projects carried out with families within the framework of educational communities during the first year of COVID 19 in Spain were analyzed following the social work method to assess the results of the initiatives applied in this emerging field. Thus, to achieve the objective of this study, a qualitative, mixed, exploratory, and holistic design was chosen. Interviews were conducted with directors and educators, and a questionnaire was administered to the participating families. The data collected was analyzed using the content analysis technique according to the variables that define the object of study. The results show that when art is collaboratively created and social work operates through these participatory practices, a synergistic relationship emerges that facilitates the achievement of objectives through reflective processes. These processes support emotional self-regulation and, when materialized through installed artworks, promote attitudinal change and foster interinstitutional collaboration.

Keywords: Family Social Work, Art Education, Art, COVID-19, Childhood, Methodology

Introduction

Traditionally, art and social work have been regarded as distinct fields of knowledge: the former associated with symbolic and aesthetic expression, the latter with technical intervention in the social sphere (López Peláez et al. 2020). However, the boundaries between disciplines become increasingly blurred in the face of complex crises such as the COVID 19 pandemic or climate emergencies, where human suffering, the need for resilience, and community action are deeply intertwined (Giæver and Russell 2024; Voški Wong-Parodi and Ardoin 2024).

This article is guided by the following research question: How can artistic and participatory interventions contribute to emotional self-regulation, community strengthening, and psychosocial resilience in the context of environmental crises associated with climate change, and what are the implications for adaptation strategies and public policy? Drawing on experiences conducted in educational communities during the first year of the COVID-19 pandemic in Spain, we propose a conceptual framework that, although grounded in that

specific context, is applicable to other crisis scenarios such as natural disasters, water insecurity, and climate-induced anxiety (Easton-Gómez et al. 2022; Clayton and Ogunbode 2023).

Recent studies demonstrate that collective emotions play a decisive role in shaping both climate risk perception and response capacity (Kovács et al. 2024; Zeier et al. 2025). In this regard, we propose distinguishing between two complementary dimensions of resilience:

The first dimension is personal resilience, defined as the ability to self-regulate emotionally, cope adaptively, and recover individually from stress, while the second is community resilience, understood as the collective capacity to sustain bonds, activate shared resources, and preserve a sense of belonging in the face of adversity (Samuel et al. 2024).

Art, far from being a purely expressive tool, is conceived here as an interdisciplinary device that fosters processes of critical reflection, emotional transformation, and participatory action. Several studies have shown that creative activities promote emotional self-regulation (Fancourt et al. 2019; Lee and Choi 2023), enhance ecosocial learning in school settings (Heinemeyer et al. 2024), and open up symbolic spaces for vulnerable communities facing ecological crises (Brice and Arconada 2017; Brown et al. 2017).

Moreover, artistic approaches enable the processing of subjective experiences of ecological grief, uncertainty, or emotional paralysis through non-pathologizing and culturally situated frameworks (Lockwood 2016; Tait 2024). The collective creation of installations, artworks, or visual narratives serves as a mediating platform between lived experience and the public sphere, facilitating a transition from vulnerability to agency (McKinlay 2024; Weder 2022).

This article presents a conceptual model of artistic intervention in climate-related crises, integrating emotional self-regulation, community resilience, ecosocial learning, and political agency. This perspective aligns with the relational turn in social work and critical pedagogy and invites novel forms of collaboration between artists, mental health professionals, and socio-environmental practitioners (Wardle 2025; Robbie and Warren 2021). Finally, this approach offers relevant insights for the development of people-centered climate adaptation strategies, recognizing art not only as a therapeutic vehicle but also as a symbolic infrastructure for ecological and emotional resilience (Smith et al. 2025; Kalaidjian 2025).

Conceptual Framework: Participatory Arts in the Climate Crisis

To address the challenges posed by climate change-related crises, this study adopts a conceptual framework that illustrates how artistic and participatory interventions contribute to emotional self-regulation, community resilience, and climate adaptation (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

Artistic and participatory practices—such as community-based art, collaborative storytelling, and collective installations—serve as catalysts that foster emotional processing and social engagement. As noted by Fancourt et al. (2019) and Hui et al. (2019), these practices provide both symbolic and embodied tools that facilitate individual emotional regulation.

From an individual perspective, such interventions support emotional self-regulation by enabling the expression of grief, anxiety, and eco-emotions (Clayton and Ogunbode 2023; Voşki et al. 2024). At the collective level, they contribute to community resilience through the construction of shared narratives and mutual support (Brice and Arconada 2017; Easton-Gómez et al. 2022). Simultaneously, they stimulate ecosocial learning, promoting critical awareness, climate literacy, and pro-environmental attitudes (Brown et al. 2017; Heinemeyer et al. 2024).

These three intermediate outcomes converge in agency and adaptation: a dynamic process through which individuals and communities build capacities to implement proactive strategies in the face of environmental threats (Giæver and Russell 2024). Ultimately, these processes can inform institutional and policy changes, offering inclusive, creative, and emotionally responsive models of climate action (Smith et al. 2025; McKinlay 2024).

Indeed, the climate crisis presents challenges of enormous complexity that demand integrated approaches capable of addressing the ecological, social, emotional, and cultural dimensions of the problem. In this context, the interdisciplinary intersection of art, social work, and ecopsychology emerges as a fertile ground for generating innovative, inclusive, and transformative responses (Voşki et al. 2024; Fancourt et al. 2019).

These disciplines share a common concern for well-being, agency, and social transformation. Art contributes symbolic forms of representation, expression, and connection; social work offers a structural perspective focused on justice and context-sensitive intervention; and ecopsychology provides frameworks to understand the links between

emotional suffering and environmental degradation. Their convergence enables the design of integrated interventions that connect psychosocial care with ecological sustainability.

Examples of this interdisciplinary synergy are already being successfully implemented. Heinemeyer et al. (2024) demonstrate how participatory storytelling can be employed as a pedagogical tool in secondary schools, engaging young people with the challenges of climate change from an emotional and creative perspective. McKinlay (2024) documents an activist experiment in which art and science collaborate in community settings to raise awareness about air quality and its health impacts, fostering collective responses. Wardle (2025), in turn, shows how nature-based art therapy can support children's emotional regulation in the face of the climate crisis, integrating art, mental health, and environmental connectedness.

These cases illustrate that art does not operate in isolation: its effectiveness is amplified when embedded within collaborative ecosystems involving social workers, educators, therapists, and community agents. This interdisciplinary network is crucial to responding sensitively and contextually to climate impacts, particularly among vulnerable populations (Smith et al. 2025; McKinlay 2024).

While the COVID-19 pandemic served as the original empirical context for our study, the theoretical framework proposed here is explicitly extended to other climate-related crises. These include slow-onset environmental changes such as droughts and eco-anxiety, as well as acute disasters requiring urgent community responses and psychological recovery. Drawing on recent climate adaptation literature, our model aligns with approaches that emphasize socio-emotional resilience, decentralized community empowerment, and culturally embedded modes of coping (Easton-Gómez et al. 2022; Smith et al. 2025; Samuel et al. 2024). By situating artistic interventions within these broader frameworks, the study offers a scalable and transferable perspective that informs both grassroots action and institutional strategies.

Method

Object of the Study and Context of the Research

This study aims to analyze how artistic techniques can be applied as tools within social work to promote emotional self-regulation and community resilience among families facing traumatic situations. Specifically, the research explores the potential of participatory art to support educational communities in crisis contexts and examines its integration within social work methodologies.

A total of eighteen references on art, art education, and COVID 19 in Spain were reviewed, only two of which involved social interventions using artistic mediation with families of children under the age of three during the pandemic. This study focuses on these two projects—*Infancias confinadas* and *FamiliarizArte*—to assess their impact and contribute to the professional development of the emerging field of artistic social work.

Participants

The analysis focuses on the institutional framework that gave rise to the artistic projects *Infancias confinadas* and *FamiliarizArte*, developed in two nursery schools in A Coruña (Spain), in collaboration with the city's Museum of Fine Arts and the Master's program in Art Education at the Valladolid University. The entire educational community—school leadership, educators, children, and families—participated in the projects, alongside an activist social worker who facilitated coordination among the various entities. The museum provided a selection from its collection to support the creation of a photo-essay that enabled reflection on the experience of COVID 19.

Methodological Framework

The Spanish projects *Infancias confinadas* and *FamiliarizArte* were developed within a social work methodological framework comprising five interrelated phases: assessment, diagnosis, process design, implementation, and evaluation (López Peláez et al. 2020). Throughout these processes, artistic techniques were integrated as tools for social intervention, given their alignment with the objectives of social work—namely, to foster awareness, attitudinal change, cohesion, and empowerment.

This approach is particularly suitable in crisis contexts such as the COVID-19 pandemic, which significantly impacted both school and family life. As Penketh and Riding (2023) argue, when art is connected to well-being, it enables individuals, groups, and communities to better adapt to their environment, even under unfavorable conditions for sociability. In this regard, both projects are framed within the social model of resilience, which advocates the use of resources that strengthen people and communities under stress (López Peláez et al. 2020). The aim of this research is to assess the outcomes and contribute to the theoretical construction of the emerging field of artistic social work.

Methodological Approach and Research Design

The main objective of this study is to examine how artistic and participatory practices can support emotional self-regulation, strengthen community ties, and foster psychosocial resilience in crisis contexts. Specifically, we aim to analyze their applicability within educational communities during the COVID-19 pandemic and assess their relevance for broader climate-related crises. This objective guided the selection of a mixed, exploratory, and holistic design, aligned with the interdisciplinary nature of the research and the emerging intersections between art, social work, and climate adaptation.

This research adopts a qualitative approach, suitable for exploring participants' perspectives and understanding the context through an interdisciplinary lens that bridges art and social work (Hammersley and Atkinson 1994). The methodological design is mixed,

exploratory, and holistic: mixed due to the combined use of techniques and instruments (Reidl 2012); exploratory, as it begins with interviews conducted with teachers, school leaders, museum staff, and an activist social worker, whose contributions guided the design of the open-ended questionnaire addressed to families (Ruiz-Olabuénaga 2012; Alvira 2002); and holistic, as the activities address the cognitive, emotional, and bodily dimensions of participants (Moreno González 2022).

Researcher Positionality

As practitioners-researchers working at the intersection of social work, arts education, and community practice, we acknowledge that our professional and disciplinary backgrounds influenced both the design and the interpretation of this study. One author has a long-standing trajectory in community social work with families and early childhood education, while the other brings expertise in participatory art and pedagogical mediation in museum contexts. These perspectives shaped the selection of methods, the facilitation of artistic activities, and the interpretation of emergent narratives. To address potential biases and maintain critical reflexivity, we adopted several strategies: triangulating data sources (educators, families, and institutional staff), engaging in peer debriefing with the GIMUPAY research group, and incorporating participants' voices as interpretive agents rather than passive subjects. We consider this reflexive stance essential in contexts where researcher involvement is not only inevitable but constitutive of the participatory process itself.

Dimensions, Specific Objectives, and Variables

To operationalize the general objective, three dimensions were defined based on the main impacts of COVID 19, aligned with the effects of the pandemic (Ruiz-Olabuénaga 2012). The crisis triggered a global and devastating experience of grief that profoundly affected individuals, marking a before and after in their life trajectories (Acinas 2021). This grief, beyond personal loss, also involved processes of adaptation and resilience (Voški et al. 2024). In many cases, it was accompanied by trauma, understood as a psychological wound that renders previous adaptive mechanisms ineffective (Zeier et al. 2025). In Spain, one notable response was vicarious aggression, particularly during the second and third waves, whereby others were blamed for risky behaviors not acknowledged in oneself.

In this context, artistic projects were implemented following the social work method, aiming to improve well-being through artistic actions embedded in social intervention processes (López Peláez et al. 2020). The analysis of these initiatives helped define the research object, structured into dimensions, specific objectives, and variables, in coherence with the institutional framework described (see Table 1).

Table 1: Operationalization of the Object of Study

<i>Dimensions</i>	<i>Specific Object</i>	<i>Variables</i>
1. The trauma of COVID 19 and confinement	1.1. Assess the suitability of artistic techniques to elaborate, within the scope of the educational community, the trauma from COVID 19 and home confinement through the method of social work	1.1.1. Impacts of the artistic projects
2. Vicarious aggressiveness during the second and third waves of COVID 19	2.1. To determine the capacity of artistic techniques to provoke cognitive and attitudinal changes in the educational community through social work-based methods	2.1.1. Cognitive and attitudinal change in the educational communities
3. Mass vaccination and coexistence with the COVID-19 disease	3.1. To analyze the adequacy of artistic techniques to represent and symbolize the discourse of the collective subject generated by community social work	3.1.1. Functioning of the activist methodology (By activist methodology, we mean the use of artistic practices as resources of social work, that is, a combination of “artist” and “activist”)

The Artistic Techniques Applied to Achieve Socio-Educational Objectives

In the *Infancias confinadas* and *FamiliarizArte* projects, two artistic techniques were employed to achieve socio-educational goals: installation art and artistic contemplation. The selected materials and artworks were chosen for their symbolic, emotional, and contextual relevance to the experiences of the participating families during the pandemic, thereby enabling processes of collective reflection and personal connection.

Installation art, understood as a contemporary practice that arranges physical, visual, or sound materials in space to produce meaning and provoke sensory experiences (Larrañaga 2001), took shape in two different installations.

In *Infancias confinadas* (May 2020), the materials for the proposed installation were carefully selected based on narratives gathered during preparatory sessions with the participating families. The artistic choices were guided by the intention to symbolically represent key emotional and social dimensions of the lockdown.

The installation was structured around three metaphorical elements: (1) glass bottles of various sizes, representing the shared yet individually experienced isolation of each family; (2) written messages contributed by the families, capturing their lived experiences during confinement; and (3) a circular arrangement around the school building, alluding to the global and collective nature of the pandemic. Although the installation could not be physically

implemented due to health restrictions, it was conceived as a space for shared reflection and recognition (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Image of the Project *Infancias Confinadas*: Installation

In *FamiliarizArte* (June 2021), coinciding with the start of vaccination, the installation used open boxes, colored yarn, and red and white barrier tape. This composition represented both the collective experience and the reclaiming of public space. It was built by the families themselves through a game-based activity that encouraged participatory engagement.

The second technique, artistic contemplation, was developed through a photo-essay using artworks from the Museo de Belas Artes da Coruña. According to Marín-Viadel and Roldán (2017), this form of visual narrative facilitates hermeneutical reflection on the meaning of visual discourse. In *FamiliarizArte*, the selected artworks adhered to three criteria: (1) thematic resonance with pandemic-related emotions (e.g., astonishment, isolation, hope); (2) visual recognizability to encourage intuitive engagement; and (3) symbolic potential to prompt discussion about everyday life under social restrictions. The works—*Xentes que ollan*, by Díaz Pardo; *Casas* by Tenreiro, *Vista da Coruña* by Lugrís; and *Zoológico*, by Rivera—were curated to guide participants through an emotional journey of collective memory (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Image of the Project *FamiliarizArte*: Installation

In this sense, in the *FamiliarizArte* project, the works included in the photo-essay were carefully selected by the facilitators in collaboration with the museum educators, following three main criteria: (1) thematic resonance with emotions experienced during the pandemic (such as astonishment, isolation, or hope); (2) visual recognizability to facilitate intuitive engagement by diverse families; and (3) symbolic potential to provoke discussion about everyday life under social restrictions. The purpose of the deductive photo-essay was to provoke an emotional journey regarding what happened (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Photo-Essay Created from the Images Donated by the Museo de Belas Artes da Coruña for the *FamiliarizArte* Project

Source: Díaz 1963, Tenreiro 1971, Lugrís 1959, and Rivera 1950

The Data Collection Process

To address the diversity of participants—families, cultural institutions, and professionals—two data collection techniques were employed: semi-structured interviews (fifteen in total) with school directors and educators, staff from the Museum of Fine Arts, and the social worker who initiated the project; and an open-ended questionnaire sent to 159 families, achieving an 81% response rate.

The choice of methods aligns with the exploratory nature of the study. The interviews helped identify key topics, given the professionals' close contact with families throughout the project. Data collection unfolded in three phases, with voluntary participation guaranteed at all times. Following the interviews, the questionnaire was distributed to families via the nursery schools.

Ethical Aspects of Research

The study adhered to ethical research standards and was approved by the Ethics Committee of the University of Valladolid (PI 23-3402 NO HCUV). Participants were informed about the purpose and procedures of the study and gave their informed consent, guaranteeing data confidentiality, limited use for academic purposes, and secure data storage.

Data Analysis Process

The collected information was analyzed using content analysis (Valles 1997), based on pre-established dimensions and variables. The findings were compiled into a results report, which also included images of the artistic practices.

In addition to verbal data, the artistic practices generated by the participants—such as proposed installations, symbolic materials, and visual compositions—were also considered as discursive artifacts and analyzed as part of the data corpus. These artistic outputs were examined through hermeneutic content analysis, identifying recurring visual metaphors, symbolic representations, and collective narratives expressed through the artistic elements. This interpretive approach allowed us to triangulate visual and verbal data, deepening our understanding of the emotional and social experiences conveyed by the families.

Notably, the success or suitability of the techniques (i.e., the results) of the project evaluation were discussed by members of the GIMUPAY research group (Research Group, Pedagogical Museum of Children's Art) at the Valladolid University in order to reach a positive consensus on its validity.

Results

Results Associated with Dimensions 1 and 2

The study evaluated the effectiveness of artistic techniques, applied through artistic social work, to process the trauma caused by the COVID-19 lockdown and to generate cognitive and attitudinal changes related to aggressiveness. High participation was notable: 159 families and five institutions took part, with an 81% questionnaire response rate and full acceptance of interviews, all on a voluntary basis.

Artistic contemplation in the *Infancias confinadas* and *FamiliarizArte* projects played a central role in processing trauma and fostering reflective change. From the perspective of the activist social worker, “listening and artistic contemplation impacted the educational communities in the expected way, provoking communication and a reflective thread, from which a choral story was extracted” that, “in addition to generating cohesion and empathy,” ensured in the *Infancias confinadas* project “that schools became aware of the situation of families during confinement and could prepare the reception of children, as well as address the doubts and fears of families.” In the case of *FamiliarizArte*, it allowed families “to elaborate a common, reflective and experiential narrative of everything that happened during the first year of the pandemic.”

According to the activist social worker, the visual narrative “provoked an intimate, reflective, and calm environment, which enabled families and schools to share feelings of fear, panic, and uncertainty, and to transform them into acceptance and an opportunity to change everything that hindered sociability, equity, and justice.” In this sense, “a feeling of global consciousness, of humanity, emerged, generating commitment, care, and respect for others.”

With regard to the evaluation of the visual narrative composed from the Museum’s artworks, the early childhood educators noted that the paintings “capture the most significant situations of this lived period” and therefore allow “reflection on the immense consequences that are only beginning to become visible.” They also emphasized that the selection and arrangement of the images “was a useful tool that allowed emotions derived from confinement to be expressed,” particularly in relation to “children aged 0 to 3 years, who may have difficulties in choosing and naming appropriate words.” As a result, “the contemplation of the artworks allowed them to identify and communicate their emotions.”

The cognitive and attitudinal changes brought about by artistic contemplation were described by educators from both nursery schools as “gradual. From tension and uncertainty, we passed—all of us, too—to a feeling of acceptance and from there to hope,” as they realized that “our way of thinking and acting affects others, the whole of society” and that “we have a responsibility, and fulfilling it helps us.”

From the perspective of the Museo de Belas Artes de A Coruña, one educator highlighted that “the choice of works was especially significant, especially considering that they were

created in a time long before the pandemic,” and added that “although it is impossible, it seems that they were designed for this moment, to generate reflection and lead us to a change of attitude; art is universal.”

The museum’s curator and head of dissemination emphasized that “the most innovative aspect of the project is the exhibition of the works, in a virtual document, which allows to guide the thought towards an end, the feelings associated with the COVID-19 situation.” Additionally, another educator noted that “it is very provocative and performative to take a work out of the museum context, allowing to establish a new ‘unforeseen’ discourse, generated in dialogue with the families of the school.”

Families reported that the selected artworks, despite being created prior to the pandemic, “represent and evoke the main feelings, emotions, and moments derived from COVID-19,” demonstrating that emotions such as “fear, uncertainty, loneliness, and hope are universal and timeless,” capable of generating “cohesion and empathy, even through time and space.” They also emphasized that “art is so subjective that any work allows us to interpret social reality, since it is the gaze of the spectator that places it and associates it with one or another context.”

Regarding specific works, families noted that those by Antonio Tenreiro Casas and *Lago Rivera Zoológico* “perfectly describe the confinement and limitations[...]of the so-called new normal.” *Vista da Coruña*, by Urbano Lugrís, was described as “the landscape we saw from our window every day,” and “it represents, perfectly, the desire to go out and travel the edge of the ocean.” As for *Xentes de ollan* by Díaz Pardo, it allowed families to place the confusion associated with the declaration of the state of emergency: “in our opinion, the faces clearly reflected the concern for the situation,” as well as “panic and absolute lack of control.”

Concerning the role of artistic installations in *Infancias confinadas* and *FamiliarizArte*, their potential for processing trauma and generating cognitive and attitudinal change was highlighted. In *Infancias confinadas*, the installations enabled families “to symbolize the family experience of confinement, which, when shared and represented in a collaborative artistic proposal, generated from the messages offered by families during the first lockdown, became community and meaningful.” In *FamiliarizArte*, the installation “facilitated the interaction of families in a public space, through the symbolic and shared play generated by the chosen objects” (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Messages from the Educational Community

Both proposals “generated in the participants a cognitive change,” shifting from fear and uncertainty “to hope and even to a positive assessment of what happened[...]as an opportunity for attitudinal change.”

According to the educators and school leadership, “the raw material was the communication generated...which gave rise to a discourse, which for me is hope,” and “made families value the school’s work very positively[...]and that helped us a lot the following year.”

Families emphasized that the installations facilitated deep connections between experience and representation, fostering meaningful community reflection.

In *Infancias confinadas*, the art installation enabled participants “to share the fears, experiences, and small hopes associated with the new normal.” As one participant stated, “when you looked at the bottles, you first looked for those of your family...but then you stopped before those of others...because we all feel fear...but also hope,” reflecting a common desire “for a shared future.”

In *FamiliarizArte*, families described the experience as deeply meaningful: “the play installation was wonderful...What a good feeling to be together again, around something beautiful, created for us.” This experience strengthened the relationship with the school:

“they have listened to us, they have understood our need for interaction.” Furthermore, “the play, the beauty, made me talk and helped me to approach other parents.”

Children’s creativity was especially highlighted: “I learned that we should not fall asleep when it comes to art and creativity,” since “children are the first artists. Through play, they are capable of creating wonderful things.”

Finally, empathy emerged as a key outcome: “being together, I understood that we had all gone through the same thing,” and “I discovered myself thinking about the other families...and I thought it was beautiful.”

Results Associated with Dimension 3

The adequacy of artistic techniques to represent and symbolize the discourse of the collective subject generated by the community social work, regarding the coexistence with the disease after mass vaccination.

From the perspective of the Artist Social Worker, “the objectives of the *Infancias confinadas* and *FamilizArte* projects: to symbolise the confinement of the educational community and favour the recovery of public space and coexistence, as well as provoking, through artistic contemplation, an atmosphere of reflection that leads to a cognitive change, has been fulfilled; artistic social work has worked.” In his opinion, “art needs an intervention methodology that allows it to exercise its transformative capacity, and the method of social work is adequate, especially with regard to the resilience model. It is a new, emerging field in which art and social work have much to say to each other.”

For the educators of the children’s school, the development of the projects, “this way of doing so different,” “generates community and encounters,” because “it is the seed of inter-institutional collaboration, this being very positive for the school, in the sense that the main beneficiaries of all this effort have been families and children, but also the collaborating entities in terms of the links that have been created, from this initiative, new projects will be born.” Therefore, after reflecting on the project, an educator notes that “the connections between families, schools and institutions should be more fluid and habitual and this project has demonstrated this. Together, we work harder and better.”

Thus, the schools emphasize that one of the main benefits of the methodology is “the joint work, since it is more enriching,” an aspect that also indicates that the educators of the Museum “working with other institutions allows us to deepen art, generating new contexts.”

Thus, the children’s school considers that the purpose of the projects has been achieved: “all participants, families, children, and institutions have learned that, through art, you can not only enjoy it, favour imagination and creativity, as well as interpret everything we see and observe looking at an artistic work, causing a curious and observant attitude that leads people to imagine themselves as protagonists of the works they contemplate.” Similarly, the study notes that the people who participated in the projects “learned to look at and value what a

work can tell. Artistic creation is not a dead language, but is always alive, being meaningful to the eyes that look at and browse life.”

In relation to the methodology of community-based artistic social work, representatives from the museum emphasized that “it would not have been possible to reach the educational community without the participatory and creative approach adopted in the project.” They highlighted the importance of “generating dynamics that are open to a diverse and constantly evolving society, especially in times of crisis.” This perspective aligns with the core objectives of the initiative. As they noted, “the response has positively surprised us”; the project “has been a very interesting action that strengthened our ties with the community” and “has allowed the museum to rethink the collection—not only as a curatorial discourse, but also as a tool and foundation for social dialogue.”

From the perspective of families, these projects “unite and enrich” by allowing people “to know better the environment, the resources of the community and the people.” “I never thought that art was good for this. It seemed passive to me, but it’s not like that; it was the piece that changed everything” (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Play and Art

Discussion and Conclusion

This discussion revisits the central objective of the study: to examine the potential integration of participatory artistic practices into social work as a means to foster emotional self-regulation, enhance psychosocial resilience, and strengthen community ties in crisis contexts. Building on the methodological framework outlined previously, we now interpret the findings in light of this aim, examining their relevance to both the COVID-19 context and broader applications in climate-related emergencies and educational settings.

This qualitative study, which uses art to address the trauma caused by COVID 19, reveals that participants—particularly families—have transformed the threat of the disease into an opportunity to strengthen the educational community. Although fear and anxiety related to

the pandemic and misinformation persist, there is evidence of an increased coping capacity among the participants.

Moreover, although this study was initially framed within the context of the COVID-19 pandemic, the findings have broader implications for climate resilience and disaster recovery. The development of emotional self-regulation, social cohesion, and shared narratives through art-based interventions are equally relevant in the face of environmental threats. As Easton-Gómez et al. (2022) and Giæver and Russell (2024) suggest, the capacity to transform emotional responses into collective action is a cornerstone of psychosocial resilience in both health and climate crises.

Thus, as Penketh and Riding (2023) point out, it is observed, always within the framework of this research, that artistic activities are an excellent mediator between the “self” and the “environment,” especially when the latter is unstable and generates insecurity, since engagement in artistic projects has contributed to improving the mental well-being of the participants, who have discovered in themselves and their community environment strengths that lead to not only individual but also community resilience (Fancourt and Finn 2019).

In this sense, the *Infancias confinadas* and *FamiliarizArte* projects, by committing art to achieve well-being, have allowed the involved agents and agencies to create, through art, a channel of emotional communication between families and cultural and educational institutions. This, in turn, evidences how families and institutions have been able to turn the threat of COVID 19 into an opportunity to engage in community projects. Hence, we can speak of cognitive change and social cohesion in the framework of this research (Thomson and Chatterjee 2022).

Moreover, looking at the professionals who participated in the artistic projects, the results obtained show that working in a network that proposes artistic activities increases community cohesion and, consequently, a reduction in stress, since, instead of facing the difficulties derived from COVID 19 alone, they have managed to generate a joint strategy within the framework of their institution, reducing isolation and improving coping capacity (World Health Organization 2023). While the benefits of artistic methodologies are evident in terms of engagement and affective transformation, it is important to acknowledge potential limitations and to situate them within a broader ecosystem of crisis intervention strategies. Traditional methods of social work—such as cognitive behavioral therapy, case management, or community organizing—offer structured and scalable tools for intervention that may complement or even surpass the impact of artistic approaches in certain contexts (Clayton and Ogunbode 2023; Robbie and Warren 2021). Therefore, it is critical to avoid aesthetic idealism and instead adopt a pragmatic perspective that considers art as part of an interdisciplinary response tool kit. This echoes the conclusions reached by Fancourt et al. (2020) and the All-Parliamentary Group on Arts, Health, and Wellbeing (2017).

Thus, based on the analysis of the data and its contextualization in the academic literature, it is possible to affirm that there is a symbiotic relationship between art and social

work (Moreno González 2022), given that artistic practices function as an excellent mediating tool between the object of social work and the community subject, which can be seen in the cohesive role of art and its ability to bring people together in the expression of a shared experience (in this case, COVID 19). This communal and collective expression is the fruit of a support network linked to a process of personal and group change (Mundet et al. 2015; Thomson and Chatterjee 2022). Nonetheless, several limitations must be acknowledged regarding art-based interventions. Firstly, the subjective nature of aesthetic experience introduces interpretive variability—what resonates with one participant may alienate another. Secondly, accessibility may be limited by cultural capital, prior exposure to artistic forms, or language. Lastly, there is a risk of symbolic overreach, wherein the transformation attributed to artistic output may be more reflective than structural. Future studies should explore these tensions to enhance the robustness and equity of participatory arts in crisis contexts (Voški et al. 2024; Weder 2022).

Consequently, we can see how, even in situations as adverse as the social isolation derived from COVID 19, artistic practices allow human beings to attach themselves to an idea that includes others, favoring social commitment (Fancourt et al. 2020; All-Parliamentary Group on Arts, Health, and Wellbeing 2017). This issue can be seen in the high participation rates, particularly regarding the response rate obtained in the questionnaire (81%), much higher than that estimated as adequate (33%), especially considering that participation both in the artistic projects and in the subsequent research process was voluntary.

According to dimension 1, and within the framework of the projects analyzed, artistic techniques favored social cohesion, bringing together not only people but also institutions and the community; thus, it is possible to affirm, as the WHO notes, that art is capable of sowing the seed of cooperation in individuals, groups, and communities (Fancourt and Finn 2019).

In the *Infancias confinadas* project, the raw material of the community installation is the experience of confinement, that is, the micro-stories contributed by families, their fears, anecdotes, and small hopes that, when framed within a broader narrative, allow us to find ourselves or experience community belonging, reducing the feeling of social isolation (Zaliasnik 2017; Mak et al. 2021).

In this sense, in terms of dimension 2, joint participation in a project such as *Infancias confinadas*, which focused on self-knowledge, motivation, and hope, led to a better therapeutic alliance between families and educators, an issue that the WHO also refers to in its global report (Fancourt and Finn 2019).

Artistic contemplation, as seen in the FamilizArte project, allows participants to bring to light everyday feelings, relativizing the weight of those feelings, and to appreciate their own ability to cope, which, in turn, fosters motivation and resilience (Manonelles 2011; Fancourt et al. 2019).

However, according to dimension 3, the social processes, when expressed in an artistic way, also allow participants to process the experience of COVID 19 through the creative

process because art “can reach feelings, the heart and mind in an unconscious way” (Carrascal and Solera 2014, 16).

The playful character of art and its continuous dynamism applied within the methodological framework of social work allows us to focus the intervention goals on the process and the experience rather than on the final result (López Peláez et al. 2020). Hence, the experience becomes the chisel that traces the potentiality of form in sculpture.

Thus, it is important to note that art by itself does not heal or save anyone, but, as committed art, it makes a difference to the environment in which it is applied, becoming a powerful tool for group and community social work.

From the analysis and discussion of the results, the following conclusions can be drawn. Although this is a qualitative study limited to two projects—*Infancias confinadas* and *FamiliarizArte*—focused on artistic interventions in early childhood educational communities during the COVID-19 pandemic, the data was rigorously analyzed using a framework grounded in social work methodology. Specifically, the process included five phases: diagnosis, planning, implementation, evaluation, and feedback. Data collection combined semi-structured interviews with key professionals ($n = 15$) and open-ended questionnaires for families ($n = 159$, with an 81% response rate). The information was processed using content analysis, guided by previously established dimensions and variables related to trauma, vicarious aggressiveness, and emotional representation. To ensure methodological soundness, the MUPAI Research Group at the Valladolid University independently reviewed the coding and interpretation of the findings, validating the coherence and consistency of the results.

In this context, these elements support the internal validity of the study, while acknowledging that the findings are not intended for statistical generalization. In light of the intensifying climate crisis, this study’s insights are relevant for informing people-centered adaptation strategies. Artistic and participatory approaches can be aligned with adaptation frameworks that emphasize social learning, collective agency, and emotional infrastructure as key dimensions of community resilience (Smith et al. 2025; Kalaidjian 2025). By mobilizing local knowledge and fostering intergenerational dialogue, art becomes a vector for inclusive adaptation policies that honor cultural and emotional diversity.

In summary, this study confirms the potential of participatory artistic interventions as a valuable methodological tool within social work practice, particularly in contexts marked by emotional trauma and collective vulnerability. By centering families’ lived experiences and promoting emotional reflection through visual and symbolic means, the initiatives analyzed demonstrate the capacity of art to activate individual agency, reinforce social bonds, and foster resilience. These findings suggest promising avenues for future interdisciplinary research and highlight the need to further systematize art-based strategies in social and educational policy frameworks addressing crises of various origins.

Despite this limitation, the results confirm the existence of a symbiotic relationship between committed artistic practices and social work, which can be seen in the object shared by both disciplines—personal and social well-being—and the cognitive change experienced by the social actor. In this sense, art and social work share skills that facilitate intervention. Thus, listening and contemplation are, in addition to the principle of social work, an artistic attitude.

This technique, called artistic contemplation, facilitated the creation of a reflective, communitarian, and sensitive thread, which provoked a community transformation. In this sense, participants turned the threat of COVID 19 into an opportunity for personal change and commitment.

On the other hand, the installed art allowed the community to symbolize and represent the experience of COVID 19 as well as to recover public spaces and social interaction while respecting sanitary measures.

In the opinion of the participants, the artistic installations generated communication between families and institutions such that shared narratives were the raw material, that is, the backbone that represented the community and generated a cooperative background.

Regarding the methodology used, the participants considered that social work methods allow art to exercise its transformative capacity; this is an emerging field in which artistic practices dialogue with social intervention, favoring the achievement of objectives. All social partners agreed that the aim of the project was achieved.

In future research, it would be appropriate to delve deeper into the actor's perspective and analyze the depth of cognitive change, that is, the extent to which it is maintained over time and extrapolated to other difficulties and/or tensions that appear in life. It also seems appropriate to study the application of other artistic techniques, such as performance, which, when applied in contexts of difficulty, allows the representation of pain, anxiety, fear, and their opposites, favoring self-knowledge and resilience.

From a reflexive standpoint, it is important to acknowledge the researchers' dual role as both facilitators and observers within the intervention process. This proximity enabled deeper insights but also necessitates awareness of potential interpretive bias. As such, triangulation of qualitative data and external validation were employed to mitigate subjectivity and enhance the credibility of findings.

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The authors declare that generative AI or AI-assisted technologies were not used in any way to prepare, write, or complete this manuscript. The authors confirm that they are the sole authors of this article and take full responsibility for the content therein, as outlined in COPE recommendations.

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Informed Consent

This study was conducted with the informed consent of all participants. Participants were informed of the study's purpose, procedures, potential risks and benefits, and their right to withdraw at any time without penalty. Written consent was obtained from all participants. The study protocol was approved by the University of Valladolid (PI 23-3402 NO HCUV)

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest.

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